

Carbon Allocation Based on the Classification and Distribution of Endemic Species in the Caspian Forest

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SUMMARY

Carbon sequestration and allometrical relationships have great importance in the study of forest management. The purpose of this study is to examine carbon allocation and its impact on the classification of carbon stock and wet coefficient in the different processes of forest stand evolution. In this study, the full callipering (one hundred percent) method for inventory of parcel 307 in the northern part of Iran was used, as well as the software of Arc GIS 9.1 to map the trees in parcel 307. The first result of investigation showed that the wet coefficient in the carbon stock in the aerial part of trees in parcel 307 coefficient moisture of *Fagus orientalis* stand was $d < 30$ (0.46), $30 < x < 60$ (1.67), $60 < x < 80$ (0.45), $x > 80$ (0.43). The coefficient moisture of the *Quercus castanifolia* stand was $d < 30$ (0.46), $30 < x < 60$ (0.38), $60 < x < 80$ (46.6), $x > 80$ (0.45). As well as the coefficient moisture of the *Alnus subcordata* stand, it was $d < 30$ (0.44), $30 < x < 60$ (0.46), $60 < x < 80$ (0.46), and $x > 80$ (0.42), respectively. This research showed that the trees of *Quercus castanifolia* =data have the highest carbon sequestration in diameter ($30 < x < 60$ cm). As well as in this investigation, it was demonstrated that *Quercus. Castanifolia* trees with a diameter of $30 < x < 60$ cm had the highest absorption of carbon from the atmosphere compared to *Quercus castanifolia* stands. The result of this investigation showed that the stand of *T. begonifolia* had wet coefficients of $d < 30$ (0/47), $30 < x < 60$ (0.46), $60 < x < 80$ (5.7), and $x > 80$ (0/71), respectively. This investigation proved that the process of carbon sequestration in different periods of evolution has mobility between the atmosphere and coverage plants.

Keywords: Carbon, Endemic species, Caspian Forest, Distribution

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INTRODUCTION

One of the most common ecosystem goods and services is carbon sequestration. Carbon sequestration, or carbon deposition, is any type of activity that increases carbon reserves and transfers them from the atmosphere into the soil (Lal et al., 2004). The amount of carbon in trees is calculated through biomass, and the biomass of trees has several components. Forests are a source of carbon storage, and this source includes the biomass above and below the tree, which includes dead wood, organic material covering the forest floor, and soil. One of the goals of reducing

forest destruction is to preserve the above-ground biomass (Naver et al., 2009). The biomass of trees has several components and includes the biomass of the main branch, secondary branches, and other tree components (Snowdon et al., 2002).

The high biomass of upper limbs changes faster than other carbon stocks against the change of use. For this reason, determining the amount of carbon in treetop organs in forest ecosystems is of interest to many researchers. In this research to measure the carbon sequestration of trees, especially in natural and mixed forests, in addition to implementing destructive and cutting methods, it is very difficult and costly, and in many cases, it is impossible due to management limitations. Plant biomass studies, especially on trees, in addition to taking a lot of time and spending a lot of energy, are mostly done at small levels, and their information sources are less than other studies (Ketterings et al., 2006). For this reason, the researchers decided to determine the equations to calculate the biomass; all of these methods are based on the allometric relations of the biomass of the trees. Allometric relationships are actually linear equations that directly measure tree diameter into biomass and carbon deposited in different parts of tree species such as branches, stems, roots, and trees (Brown et al., 2002).

The use of allometric equations in the form of different linear models at very wide levels can be useful for a more accurate estimation of tree mass. In fact, allometric equations are the same relationship between the mass of trees and a series of biological and physical characteristics of trees, such as the diameter at the chest and the height of the tree trunks, which are commercially viable; of course, the models that, in addition to the diameter and height, are other tree trunks that are commercially viable; of course, the models that In addition to diameter and height, other measurable variables for trees have also been taken into consideration. It is more accurate than others (Joosten et al., 2004).

In this method, the dry weight, or the amount of carbon, is one of the variables that depend on the tree as a variable and can be easily measured in the forest or field, or the height of the tree as a variable like the diameter of the chest and chest. Allometric equations Allometric equations prepared based on diameter equal to chest and height are better than other equations prepared based on tree height and crown volume. The variables of breast diameter and tree height are widely used characteristics in determining the appropriate model for estimating tree mass (Tekleweini et al., 2002). The allometric model is the relationship between the dimensions and shapes of different organs and this model has handled the structure and dimensions of different organisms (Chen, 2010). Allometric relationships were developed in different fields such as biology, natural resources, and empirical science in the last year (West 2002). Even thereafter were developed by Geographic Science (Bettencourt et al., 2007).

Allometric relationships are tools for measuring carbon allocation (Chen and Jiang, 2007). Using incorrect and irrational methods is one of the greatest obstacles to the management of forest ecosystems that have bad effects on the well-being, community, and economy (Brown, 2002). Carbon sequestration is a different part of an organism, such as the carbon allocation trunk, carbon allocation stem, and carbon allocation crown of perennial plants (Lal, 2004). Processing carbon sequestration is different in numerous ecosystems, such as tropical and other ecosystems. Every year,

1 g/t of carbon is allocated in the process of forest plantation by humans in urban cities and in the artificial forest (Pandey, 2002). Estimation of carbon sequestration (carbon allocation) is important for forest structure, and also carbon allocation is a criteria important in the evaluation of the habitat of ecosystems and forest management (Cole and Ewel, 2006). Allometric relationships are is Tools for estimating the weight of trees using characteristic variables such as diameter and height in habitat (Losi 2003). The quantity criteria used Using of the allometric models is the correlation between diameters and carbon sequestration in perennial plants (Chave et al., 2005). The allometric relationships are empirical since they are for deciduous and green leaves (Anonymous, 2005).

In the allometric science, we often study the fresh weight and dry weight of pre-annual plants (Picard et al., 2012). The ecosystem also plays a radical role in the exchange of Carbon between the atmospheric environment and biosphere (Litton, 2007). The carbon sequestration process often depends on the species, environmental conditions, structure of the forest stand, phenology, ontogeny, and many other factors, as well as the plant. By using the photosynthesis process, the movement of carbon sequestration changes (Scott, 2000). The processes of carbon sequestration improve the moisture in the environment. In this research, we developed allometric relationships with the illative approach in the forest of Caspian (north of Iran: Laboratory of Tehran University: Educational and Research Forest). The goal of this research is an empirical illative approach to the management of Caspian Forest for estimating carbon sequestration. The purpose of this study is carbon allocation and dispensation on the classification of carbon stock and wet coefficient in the different periods of forest.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The parcel of 307 was studied in this study. This parcel was located at a range of sea level between 960 and 1080 meters. These areas always have a wet climate, and this region always has a Mediterranean climate. The Most of forests located in this region are located In this area. The dominant tree's species include *Fagus. Orientalis*, *Alnus. subcordata*, *Quercus. castaneifolia*, *Carpinus*, *betulus*, *Tillia, subcordata*, and etc., the woody plant of the distinction and stand, mainly have two or three layers, and stratification in the parcel of 397 was observed. The beech trees can also be seen individually; the existence of beech trees is an indicator of the forward movement of transformation and succession and may lead to the possibility of increasing beech in the future. The quality of the stands would improve from the North West side of the parcel to the West part of the parcel as well as the density of trees.

In these areas, there are *A. glotinosa* trees and several other shrub species. The forests in this area are mainly broad leaf. The Caspian forests are located on the southern shores of the Caspian Sea, and the area of these forests is over 50,000 square kilometers. These forests are located in the northern part of Iran. Most of the forests located in this region. This study was conducted in the Khyrud forest, which is located at 7 km from Nowshahr city. The coldest month of the year is rate and the warmest is 25/4 degrees Celsius, the average annual evaporation of Nowshahr is 1/31mm. The humidity of the outside environment of the trees is more than 75%. Tree growth in this area will reach 0.64m/s. As well as Caspian region often consist of

species such as *Carpinus betulus*, *Tillia. begonifolia*, *Fagus orientalis*, *Alnus subcordata*, and *Quercus castaneifolia*

FULL CALLIPERING (ONE HUNDRED PERCENTAGE)

For managing correctly the forest will need to collect quantitative and qualitative information on forest. Get that information be raised a variety of ways. The most common of method is the full callipering method (100% inventory). The study area boundary was determined by forest coursing. Then, to compare the random systematic sampling method with the method of full callipering (100% inventory), about 41.5 hectares of Khyrud forest were measured. In order to facilitate carrying out the procedure, in this study, only the trees that were higher than the diameter of 10 cm were measured. And in order to measure society parameters (mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation), the following relationships were used.

$$\mu_x = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i}{N}$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N x_i^2 - \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^N x_i)^2}{N}}{N}}$$

$$C.V\% = \frac{\sigma}{\mu_x}$$

μ_x :The actual average community, x_i :Measurable parameter in the community
 N :The number of individuals' society, σ : Standard deviation, $C.V\%$: Coefficient of variation

ALOMETRIC RELATIONSHIPS

In this study has been to four methods for Method's for calculating carbon sequestratio by the approximate method, which are described as follows: The equation of each of these methods is explained. In this regard, the unit of measurement is this, and the unit of measurement will be the height of the foot. The value of 1 inch is equal to 2.54 cm. Each foot is equal to 30.48 cm. we want to calculate the total biomass weight, we have to consider 20% in addition to the biomass weight of the shoots and the roots to get the final biomass weight.

Table 1: Relationship of biometric and allometric.

Relationship no.	Biometric and allometric indicators
-1Jan	Moisture coefficient=wetweight/dryweight
2-Jan	Specific density=dryweight/wetvolume
-3Jan	Carbon yield=dry weight×0/54
-4Jan	Tree fresh weight=dryweight×72.5%
-5Jan	Age of the tree=diameter/2×5
-6Jan	Wet-weight =(0/25diameter ² ×height)
-7Jan	Tree-weight =dryWeight×72/5%

HARVESTING OF BIOMASS CARBON STOCK

Carbon stock is usually derived from the quantity of above ground biomass so that 45% of the biomass is consist of Carbon as well as In this research were used in carbon stock estimation by using of non-destructive This Method usually has few disturbing and low cost, then destructive Method as well as in this investigation were calculated the Fresh weight and Dry Weight of the Forest Stand of parcel 307. The Forest biomass could be used to estimate carbon content within forest vegetation because 45% of the biomass is composed of carbon. Carbon content could be estimated with the following formula (Onrizal 2004):

$$\text{Carbon}_{\text{trunk}} = \text{Biomass}_{\text{Total}} \times 0.45$$

C = amount of carbon stock (t C ha)

B = biomass (t ha)

0.45 = carbon content

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Indicating the Total biomass of trees in the in the parcel of 307 with the use of the Full Callipering (one hundred percent).

Table 1- 1: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>Quercus. Castanifolia</i> stand of parcel 307.				Table1- 2: show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>F. orientalis</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weigh	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weigh	diameter
0.17	1.29	2.8	d30>	0.17	0.34	0.73	d30>
1.2	1.9	4.9	>30x60>	0.52	4.7	2.8	>30x60>
0.25	0.47	1.02	>60x80>	2.58	4.7	10.3	>60x80>
0.21	0.38	0.84	x80<	2.52	4.6	10.8	x80<
Table1- 3: Show the distribution of Carbon allocation <i>T. Begonifolia</i> in the parcel307.				Table 1- 4: shows the distribution of Carbon allocation <i>Alnus, Subcordata</i> in the parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter	carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter
0/09	0/17	0/36	d30>	0/12	0/22	0/49	d30>
0/17	0/37	0/80	>30x60>	0/26	0/49	6-Jan	>30x60>
0/04	9-Jan	0/19	>60x80>	0/33	0/62	Jan-34	>60x80>
0/17	0/32	0/69	x80<	0/68	26-Jan	7-Feb	x80<

Table 2: Show that the surface Biomass upon the ground by using of the Full Callipering (one hundred percent) in the parcel of 307.

Table 2- 1: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>Quercus castanifzlia</i> stand of parcel 307.				Table 2- 2: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>F. orientalis</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter
0.56	1.03	1.43	d30>	1.19	4.06	5.61	d30>
0.8	1.52	2.09	>30x60>	0.59	1.1	1.52	>30x60>
0.37	0.68	0.95	>60x80>	2.6	3.8	5.2	>60x80>
0.16	0.31	0.43	x80<	3.07	6.97	9.62	x80<
Table 2- 3: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation <i>T. begonifolia</i> of parcel 307.				Table2- 4: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>A. subcordata</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter
0.08	0.18	0.22	d30>	0/09	0.18	0.25	d30>
0.16	0.3	0.41	>30x60>	0/21	0.39	0.54	>30x60>
0.14	0.27	0.37	>60x80>	0/10	0.18	0.25	>60x80>
0.14	0.25	0.35	x80<	0/54	1.01	1.39	x80<

Table 3: Show that the Carbon stock of trunk of the pre- annual plant with using of the Full Callipering (one hundred percent) in the parcel of 307.

Table 3- 1: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>Quercus. Castanifolia</i> stand of parcel 307.				Table 3- 2: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>Fagus. Orientalis</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter
0.58	1.07	1.47	d30>	0.15	0.27	0.37	d30>
0.85	1.57	2.16	>30x60>	2.11	3.9	5.37	>30x60>
0/21	0.38	0.52	>60x80>	2.11	3.9	5.37	>60x80>
0/17	0.31	0.42	x80<	2.07	3.83	5.28	x80<
Table 3- 3: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation <i>Quercus. Castanifolia</i> stand of parcel 307.				Table 3- 4: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation <i>Alnus.Subcordata</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weight	diameter
0.07	0.12	0.16	d30>	0.09	0.16	0.12	d30>
0.16	0.29	0.4	>30x60>	0.22	0.4	0.55	>30x60>
0.49	0.9	1.24	>60x80>	0.27	0.5	68	>60x80>
0.14	0.25	0.34	x80<	0.56	1.03	1.42	x80<

Table 4: Show that the Carbon stock of Corona of the pre- annual plant with using of the Full Callipering (one hundred percent) in the parcel of 307.

Table 4- 1: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>Quercus. castanifolia</i> a stand of parcel 307.				Table 4- 2: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>F. orientalis</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weigh	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weigh	diameter
0.58	1.09	1.51	d30>	0.15	0.28	0/39	d30>
1.03	1.91	2.64	>30x60>	0.58	1.09	1.51	>30x60>
0.21	0.39	0.55	>60x80>	2.17	4.03	5.56	>60x80>
0.17	0.32	0.45	x80<	2.27	4.22	5.83	x80<
Table 4- 3: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation in the <i>Quercus. castanifolia</i> stand of parcel 307.				Table 4- 4: Show that distribution of Carbon allocation <i>Alnus subcordata</i> stand of parcel 307.			
Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weigh	diameter	Carbon allocation	Dry weigh	fresh weigh	diameter
0.07	0.13	0.19	d30>	0.09	0.18	0.26	d30>
0.16	0.31	0.43	>30x60>	0.22	0.41	0.57	>30x60>
0.03	0.07	0.1	>60x80>	0.28	0.52	0.72	>60x80>
0.14	0.26	0.37	x80<	0.56	1.05	1.45	x80<

In this investigation, the movement of carbon allocations in different durations of the pre-annual forest stand. This research showed that the tree's of *Quercus. Castanifolia* have the highest carbon sequestration in diameter 30<x<60 cm (Table 2-3: Table 3-3).

As well as in this investigation, were demonstrated that *Quercus. Castanifolia* trees with a diameter of 30<x<60 cm have a higher absorption of carbon from the atmosphere to *Quercus. Castanifolia* trees in the forest stand. The result of this investigation showed that the stand of *Quercus. Castanifolia* had wet wet coefficients of d<30 (0/47), 30<x<60 (0.46), 60<x>80 (5.7), and x>80 (0/71), respectively. Cofficeint moisture of *F. orientalis* stand was d<30 (0.46), 30<x<60 (1.67), 60<x>80 (0.45), x>80 (0.43) respectively. Cofficeint moisture of *Quercus. Castanifolia* stand was d<30 (0.46),30<x<60 (0.38), 60<x>80 (46.6), x>80 (0.45) respectively as well as cofficeint moisture of *Alnus. subcordata* stand was d<30 (0.44), 30<x<60 (0.46), 60<x>80 (0.46), x>80 (0.42) respectively. The result of this research verification research of health studies such as (Henry et al. 2010 and Fehrmann et al. 2006). Furthermore, the mention of wordage this research was studied. Moisture coefficient: carbon stock aerial organ of the pre-annual in parcel 307.

This investigation showed that the stand of *Quercus. Castanifolia* had a wet coefficient that was calculated. Moisture Coefficient Carbon stock aerial organ of pre-annual in parcel 307. This investigation showed that the forest stand of *T. Begonifolia* had wet coefficients of d<30 (0.81), 30<x<60 (0.73), 60<x>80 (0.72), and x>80 (0.72), respectively. Cofficeint moisture of *Fagus. orientalis* stand was d<30 (0.90), 30<x<60 (0.72), 60<x>80 (0.72), x>80 (0.72) respectively. The coefficient moisture

of *Quercus. Castanifolia* stand was $d < 30$ (0.90), $30 < x < 60$ (0.7), $60 < x > 80$ (73.17), $x > 80$ (0.7) respectively. As well as being calculated, the coefficient moisture of *Alnus, Subcordata* stood at $60 < x > 80$ (71.4), respectively. The result of this research is the phonological study (Mani, 2007). In this research, we calculated the carbon stock of the Corona pre-annual plant in parcel 307. This investigation showed that the stand of *Quercus. Castanifolia* had sufficient moisture $d < 30$ (0.68), $30 < x < 60$ (0.72), $60 < x > 80$ (0.007), and $x > 80$ (0.7), respectively. coefficient moisture of *Fagus. orientalis* stand was $d < 30$ (0.7), $30 < x < 60$ (0.7), $60 < x > 80$ (0.7), $x > 80$ (0.7). coefficient moisture of *Quercus. Castanifolia a* stand was $d < 30$ (0.7), $30 < x < 60$ (0.7), $60 < x > 80$ (0.007), and $x > 80$ (0.7), as well as coefficient moisture of *Alnus. Subcordata* stand was $d < 30$ (0.69), $30 < x < 60$ (0.71), and $60 < x > 80$ (0.7), respectively.

In this investigation, we probed that the process of carbon in different durations is completely different, and carbon in the forest stand has mobility between the atmosphere and coverage plant. The final result of this research showed that the carbon allocation had a significant effect on the growth of trees in the forest stand, and this result is similar to the results of other research on the forest stand. The result of this research showed that the habitat has a different mechanism for sequestration of carbon, such as sequestration during the growth of trees ($d < 30$ (0.68), $30 < x < 60$ (0.72), $60 < x > 80$ (0.007), and other mechanisms for saving carbon are sequestration; it's in the stem and trunk and any part of a tree.

REFERENCES

- Anonymous, A. 2005. Manual of biomass survey and analysis Forestry Research and Development Agency and Japan International cooperation Agency, 23:8-11.
- Bettencourt, L, G. Lobo, D. Helbing, C. Kühnert and G. West. 2007. Growth, innovation, scaling, and the pace of life incities .Proceeding of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America,104:7301-7306,
- Brown,S. 2002. Measuring carbon in forests: current status and future challenges. Cerrado. Forest Ecology and Management, 262:491-499.
- Cole,T.G and J. Ewel. 2006. Allometric equations for four valuable tropical trees pecies. Forest Ecology and Management, 229:351-360,
- Chave, J, S. AndaloS, N. Brown, A. and Cairns. 2005. Tree allometry and improved estimation of carbon stocks and balanceing tropical forests. Oecologia, 145:87-99.
- Chen, Y., and S. Jiang. 2007. Ananalytical process of the spatio-temporal evolution of urban systems based on allometric and fractalideas. Chaos, Solitons & Fractals, 39:49-64.
- Chen, Y. 2010. Characterizing growth and form of fractalcities with allometricscal ingex ponents. Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society,1947: 21-22.
- Fehrmann, L. and C. Klein. 2006. General considerations about the use of allometric equations for biomass estimation on the example of Norway spruce in central Europe, Forest Ecologyand Management, 236:412–421.
- Henry, M.A, W. Besnard, J. Asante, S. Eshun, R. Adu-Bredu, R. Valentini, M. Bernoux, and L. Saint-André. 2010. Wood density, Phytomass variations with in and among trees, and allometric equations in a tropical rainforest of Africa, Forest Ecology and Management, 260:1375–1388.
- Joosten, R. J. Schumacher, Wirich and A. Schulte. 2004. Evaluating tree carbon predictions for beech (*Fagussylvatica* L) in Western Germany. Forest Ecology and Management. 189:87-96.

- Ketterings, Q. M, R. Coe and C. Palm. 2001. Reducing uncertainty in the use of allometric biomass equations for predicting above ground tree biomass in mixed secondary forests. *Forest Ecology and Management*. 146:199-209.
- Lal, R. 2004. Soil carbon sequestration to mitigate climate change, *Geoderma*. 121: 1-22.
- Litton CM., Raich JW, Ryan MG. 2007. Carbon allocation in forest ecosystems *Glob Chang Biol* 13:2089–2109.
- Losi C.J., T. Siccama, T. Juan and E. Morales. 2003. Analysis of alternative methods forest carbon stock in young tropical plantations. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 184: 355-368.
- Mani, Sand N. Parthasarathy. 2007. Above-ground biomass estimation in the tropical dry ever green forests of peninsular India, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 31: 284–290,
- Návar, J. 2009. Allometric equations for tree species and carbon stocks for forests of north Western Mexico. *Forest Ecology and Management*. 257(2):427-434.
- Pandey F, and D. Narayan. 2002. Global climate change and carbon management in multifunctional forests. *Current Science* 83:593-602.
- Picard, N., S. A. Laurent and M Henry. 2012. Manual for building tree volume and biomass allometric equations: from field measurement to prediction. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, Rome and Centre de Cooperation International Agronomique pour le Développement, Montpellier, France, 36 (6): 45- 57.
- Scott N. 2000. Land cover Effects on Soil Carbon Storage in New Zealand. A National Monitoring System. *Advances in Terrestrial ecosystem carbon Inventory, Measurement and Monitoring Conference in Raleigh, North Carolina*, 23 (2): 56-58,
- Tekleweini, G., W. Ababo, W. Goitom, T. Muhamed and B. Leakemariam, B. 2019. Total volume and aboveground biomass models for *Juniperus procera* plantation in wondo genet, southern *Journal of Forestry*, (2019) 9:89-108.
- West G.B., W. Wood, and J. Brown. 2002. Allometric scaling of metabolic rate from molecules and etc. *Proceeding of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 24: 3-2478.